

1 **Resynthesizing Biology: What Comes After Reductionism?**

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6 Physicists and engineers seemed to dominate science in the prior century (1, 2). Although there
7 were many achievements in biology, the field lagged and was frequently critiqued (3-6). Then, at
8 the turn of the millennium, many argued the coming century would be an inverse; one focused
9 largely on life (7, 8). The U.S. National Academy of Sciences even formalized this vision with
10 their own report (9). Yet we are now a quarter of the way through that century, and biology
11 continues to occupy an uneasy and subordinate position in STEM. Colloquial descriptions still
12 used include words like 'soft', 'descriptive', 'messy', and 'slow'. Here, I argue that the immense
13 promise of biology, can no longer be achieved through reductionism alone, but rather through
14 convergence.

15 During the 1960s, Simpson (10) argued that the rift between reductionist and organismal
16 biologists were resolvable through clearer articulation of how the life sciences serve the
17 common good. A quick scan of the major issues facing humanity today reveals this advice is still
18 salient. Most of our grand challenges are biological in origin: pandemics, climate change,
19 biodiversity loss, food security, human health, and even integration of AI with humans. Physics
20 continues to teach us how the universe works, but biology is beginning to reveal how DNA,
21 organelles, cells, organisms and ecosystems are all interlocked. Perhaps most importantly,
22 biology is revealing the frailty of our life-support systems (11). The biology of this century must
23 therefore complete its turn towards large synthetic questions, and in doing so, fundamentally re-
24 design how science unfolds.

25

26 **Why Does Biology Trail?**

27 Biology lags the physical sciences not because it is weaker, but because it confronts one of the
28 oldest and hardest problems - the staggering complexity of nature (12). Living systems are
29 almost entirely driven by complex dynamics (12), including dense networks of feedback loops
30 operating across space and time (13-15). They are also open entities, constantly trading matter
31 and energy with their surroundings; thus they frequently operate outside normative predictive
32 bounds of thermodynamic equilibrium (5, 16). For complex dynamical systems, sensitivity to
33 initial conditions often results in the butterfly effect, thereby limiting accurate models and
34 maturation of predictive algorithms (17).

35 There are other ongoing challenges. In a short amount of time, biology paradoxically
36 transformed from data-limited and theory rich, to data rich and interpretation-limited (18, 19). As
37 E.O. Wilson noted, "*We are drowning in information, while starving for wisdom. The world
38 henceforth will be run by synthesizers, people able to put together the right information at the
39 right time, think critically about it, and make important choices wisely.*" (20) Sensor technologies,
40 genomics, remote sensing, and automation generate torrents of information, all of which can be
41 stored indefinitely now (21). Yet we often lack the conceptual frameworks to make good sense
42 of these massive data rivers (22-24). Meanwhile, support for taxonomy and natural history
43 withered (25, 26), eroding the very pillars needed to interpret complex data and recruit into the
44 field (27, 28).

45 Over recent decades, we also built a STEM system that rewards shallow thinking,
46 including speed, metrics, and output over holistic synthesis and durability of ideas (29-31). The
47 broad pattern of research becoming less disruptive over time (32) is largely congruent with that
48 architecture. Consider Peter Yodzis (the brilliant theoretical ecologist), or Peter Higgs (the Nobel
49 winning physicist) - both published sparingly, but reshaped their fields (33, 34). It is difficult to
50 imagine a Yodzis or Higgs thriving in today's science and information environment. On the more
51 functional side, while the number of US patents per capita continues to rise, the number of

52 “creative patents per capita” (i.e., those patents with a major or disruptive impact) declined to
53 very low rates (35). Speed of FDA approval for new drugs quickened, but the total number of
54 new drugs brought to market continues to drop (36).

55

56 **What Is Convergence Biology?**

57 “Convergence science” is the deliberate integration of many disciplines to solve problems no
58 single one can address (21, 37, 38). “Convergence biology” simply graphs that way-of-knowing
59 onto questions of living systems. The biological sciences are well-positioned now to benefit from
60 convergence approaches (21, 39, 40). In particular, the need to understand how patterns of all
61 the constituent parts interact across scales and levels of physical and biological organization is
62 key (41, 42). Reductionism remains vital, but seems insufficient on its own to complete the
63 complex puzzles endemic to nature or to shift paradigms (43, 44).

64 At this moment, corralling the many disciplines in service of convergence represents a
65 difficult but critical leadership challenge. Convergence science is, by design collaborative,
66 because meaningful integration cannot occur in isolation (38, 45). Convergence biology projects
67 should therefore integrate theoretical frameworks, as these are essential for shaping
68 hypotheses, inference, and interpreting complex patterns (40). It must be simultaneously multi-
69 scale and data-rich. Finally, biology must orient itself toward prediction rather than description -
70 again a historically common, and valid, critique of biology (46). The vision articulated in this
71 opinion is not new. Indeed, it echoes nascent National Science Foundation programs during the
72 early 2000s that sought to integrate “from genes to ecosystems.” This idea was correct, but the
73 tools and infrastructure were not ready. They clearly are now.

74 There are already those demonstrating the power of convergence science in practice.
75 Long before “interdisciplinary” was a strategic buzzword, these people and organizations
76 created intellectual spaces to aid in solving some very hard (often termed ‘wicked’) problems.
77 Some institutions are already adept at convergence science towards environmental and

78 sustainability work (45, 47, 48); others are increasingly seeing the value for topics like human
79 health (49, 50), such as in cancer research (21, 51). Institutions will undoubtedly target
80 convergence themes that align with and leverage their native strengths. For example,
81 universities with medical campuses may emphasize human health, whereas those in urban or
82 otherwise distinct places may prioritize regional challenges. All of this is excellent - there are
83 many uses for these approaches. But convergence biology towards answers to all the big
84 questions is the even larger vision - the one that connects every living system on the planet.
85 There is still no place it seems dedicated exclusively to this big vision.

86 Artificial intelligence (AI) will be a key piece to the puzzle. AI increasingly enables
87 syntheses (52) and learning outcomes (53) previously not possible. Machine learning and
88 recursive code will likely be used to fuse genomics, imaging, remote sensing, clinical data, and
89 ecological time series, revealing patterns that previously exceeded unaided human cognition. AI
90 mixed with collaboration and next-generation computing may finally usher us past the butterfly
91 effect on complex systems (54). That goal will be accomplished by orienting biology towards
92 probabilistic futures, attractors, and regime prediction (55) - not deterministic forecasts (56). AI
93 will not replace biologists, but it will reshape the scope of what biologists can detect. Its value is
94 in amplifying our capacity to generate, test, learn, and refine theory across complex systems.

95

96 **Clarifying the Role of Disciplines in Convergence**

97 One concern might be that convergence science implies erosion or abandonment of traditional
98 disciplines and academic programs. This is not the case. The disciplines remain major pools of
99 intellectual depth, rigor and innovation, and there is still much to be gained at the cutting edge
100 from reductionist approaches (57). Convergence science is therefore not anti-disciplinary but
101 supra-disciplinary. Within many disciplines, there is often a strong sense of history, culture, and
102 purpose (58). It would be unwise to discard or devalue these traditions. Rather, we need to seek
103 modes of harnessing them in service of larger questions that no single field can address.

104 Disciplines are therefore the bricks upon which the house of convergence biology is built. What
105 must change is not the existence or individual fields or the reductionist approach, but rather
106 isolation from one another. A related concern is that convergence science might somehow
107 further marginalize natural history and organismal biology (25, 26). In reality, the opposite is
108 true. Museums, field stations, taxonomy, and long-term research provide the empirical
109 grounding required for full-scale integration. With these resources, theories once considered
110 intractable can be tested; without them, synthesis loses biological meaning.

111

112 **Major Barriers**

113 Despite much promise, convergence biology remains plagued by recalcitrant barriers.
114 Contemporary incentive structures in STEM (academic jobs, tenure, promotion, patents)
115 continue to prioritize metrics, speed-of-production and short-term profits over intellectual depth
116 (29). Field-specific journals reinforce disciplinary boundaries and are sometimes reluctant to
117 publish cross-disciplinary work. Funding cycles are aligned with political timetables rather than
118 intellectual ones. Disciplinary boundaries remain embedded and institutionalized. For example,
119 the power structures at most universities are normally contained within colleges and
120 departments, which are still mostly segregated by discipline. Institution-wide collaborations are
121 encouraged but rarely rewarded. In practice, cross-disciplinary work can be actively
122 discouraged or viewed as a distraction from expected career pathways. During strategic
123 planning conversations at multiple institutions, junior faculty often confided that, while highly
124 interested in this kind of work, they resist such opportunities, especially while pre-tenure. Finally,
125 public trust in science is weakened when research is perceived to be aligned with ideological
126 positions rather than empirical evidence (59-61). Such perceptions can erode tenuous public
127 opinion, and lead to further funding cuts.

128

129 **Recommendations**

130 The following are a series of recommendations to aid in recentering the century of
131 biology through convergence science. (i) Through cross-agency collaboration (e.g., NSF-NIH-
132 USDA), find ways to support sustained long-term funding for convergence science. (ii)
133 Convergence-native institutions must be built and supported. Some of this will occur through re-
134 tooling of existing institutions, and is already happening to a degree. In other cases, new stand-
135 alone programs can be erected outside the confines of traditional universities and their various
136 centers and institutes. (iii) New kinds of training and workforce development programs must be
137 developed. It is okay, even desirable in many cases, to train scientific “decathletes” skilled in
138 cross-disciplinary coursework and science communication skills. (iv) Reinvest in museums, field
139 stations, taxonomy, and long-term ecological research. These are the lifeblood of biology, allow
140 for recruitment of new passionate biologists, and help detect hidden, slow or lagged processes
141 (62). (v) Protect science from capture by pursuing questions fearlessly and without ideological
142 fidelity. Leaders and science administrators should engage broadly with politics in a way that
143 helps protect and insulate science from capture, thereby actuating convergence biology, and
144 maximizing impact.

145

146 **Conclusion**

147 Convergence biology offers a powerful framework for addressing the most complex challenges
148 of our time. It also opens new pathways for probing old and primeval questions, such as the
149 origins of life, how to extend it, and the architecture of nature itself. However, realizing our
150 potential during the century of biology requires more than just new tools and big datasets. It
151 demands a degree of reform and strategic thinking in how we organize institutions, train
152 scientists, evaluate success, fund research, and engage with the public. The question is no
153 longer whether convergence biology is necessary or here, but rather, if we are daring enough to
154 build the systems required to be excellent.

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